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Sociolinguistics and Sociology of Language

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Abstract: *This article provides information about sociolinguistics and sociology of language and this about the mutual similarities and differences of the fields, about the connection of the language with the history of the society considered.*

Key words: *Sociolinguistics, sociology of language, social environment, society, topics, social factors, social psycholinguistics.*

Sociolinguistics mainly studies how social factors affect language, language Sociology studies the relationship between society and language. And so, there is a difference between sociolinguistics and sociology of language. Sociolinguistics (lot societas - society and linguistics) - linguistics, sociology (sociology), developing at the intersection of social psychology and ethnography social nature of language, social functions, influence of social factors on language mechanism and many problems related to the role of language in society is a scientific theoretical field dealing with the complex. Some of these issues (eg, "language and society") is also studied within general linguistics. The interdisciplinary status of sociolinguistics is reflected in the set of concepts used. Sociolinguistic The language community, which is considered the main concept of the analysis, is both social and linguistic symbols determined based on.

American sociolinguistics was completely different in the 1960s with methodological principles, a reaction to the basic rules of descriptive linguistics appeared in the style of Socio-Language in American Sociolinguistic Studies striving for a careful theoretical study and precise analysis of their relations observed. It should be noted that the interaction depends on the variants of language usage to more clearly express the task of studying relationships distinguish the concepts of "sociolinguistics" and "sociology of language". American according to sociolinguists, if sociolinguistics is mainly about language use considers the variability of socially modeled, and sociology is language and studies the mutual relations of the society. These two concepts are like part and whole are in a mutual relationship, and they consider the sociology of language to be a clear advantage, for him equally applying the methods of both social and linguistic research is characteristic.

In this regard, the American sociolinguist Dj. Fishman writes the following: "current at the stage of linguistic sociology researchers to the issue of systematicity, data strict focus on collection, quantitative and statistical analysis of evidence, as well as the linguistic and sociological aspects of the research are intertwined attention characterizes".

The problem of language variants is the most important for American sociolinguistics considered, they differ territorially, socially, functionally and ethnically. America one of the most important tasks of sociolinguistics is the linguistic and is to determine the socio-functional characteristics. According to their firm belief, specific features of options, their function in society, options mutual relations, the uniqueness of their owners, as well as options development and changes in their functional connections in society, the evaluation and relations of this option are studied by the sociology of language. American scientists Sepir-Whorf's hypothesis is popular among linguists continues to remain, according to which the connection between language and society is traditional not according to the "society - language" scheme, but on the basis of the reverse "language - society" scheme should be released, because the uniqueness of the language, according to Whorf, is the spiritual and makes their material life a condition, for the speakers of this language, "world leaves a unique mark on the perception of the landscape.

Language is considered changing and evolving. Language is not individual is not the same for users, nor among groups of speakers of the same language. Sociolinguistics the use of language symbolizes the main aspects of social behavior and human interaction is based on the idea that it means Thus, sociolinguists are different social how people speak differently in contexts and how people are unique and social how to use specific functions of language to convey meaning they learn. One of the sharp differences between sociolinguistics and sociolinguistics is the speech situation that is, he pays special attention to the speech process. A sociolinguist does not completely reject grammar, but he does not prioritize it, linguistic rather than grammatical. The social information value of tools takes a more important place. Therefore, social

Linguistics is the science of the construction and structure of language, while sociolinguistics is direct speech, is a field about the process of using language effectively. Society in Sociolinguistics

concept is much narrower than the concept of society in sociolinguistics. This means society participants of a specific speech process, this speech situation is understood. Sociolinguistics is social one of the sharp differences from linguistics is the special attention paid to the speech situation, that is, the speech process. From the point of view of sociolinguistics, this is not correct. After all, social Linguistics dealt with the internal system of language, its units and construction. Social Linguistics is the whole language, from the units of the phonological system to the entire language structure considers events as socially conditioned events.

Sociology (lat. socius - society, Greek. lógos - knowledge, education, understanding) is a whole about the society considered as a system and some social procedures, processes, social groups, the science of the relationship between a person and society. Sociology is created using scientific methods draw general conclusions based on empirical (based on experience) data takes Due to this, he scientifically substantiates the development models of society. Both fields deal with the interaction of society and language. The borders between these two areas are sometimes not clear. In conclusion, both Sociolinguistics and Sociology of Language are interactions between language and society are closely related areas that study the influence of.

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